

AGEING DAMAGE OF IMMERSED SYNTACTIC FOAMS UNDER COUPLED EFFECTS OF PRESSURE AND AQUEOUS CORROSION

Anouar Brini¹, Francis Pradel², Abdelwahed Benhamida¹, Helene Dumontet¹

*1 Laboratoire de Modelisation, Materiaux et Structures, LM2S, UMR 7143, CNRS
Universite Pierre et Marie Curie, Paris, France.*

*2 Division Mecanique Appliquee, Institut Franais du Petrole, IFP,
Rueil-Malmaison, France.*

SUMMARY : This paper reports the results of a research activity concerning the hygro mechanical behavior and the estimation of the lifetime of syntactic foams used as isolator of immersed oil risers. A multi-scale simplified approach was adopted based on the self-consistent method. An iterative process is also proposed to extend the field of validity of this method to high volume fraction of micro spheres and to correct the micro-stresses in order to better exploit them in damage criteria. The phenomenon of damage modeled in this work is a physico-chemical ageing of hollow glass spheres. A simplified law describing the speed of formation of a corroded layer is proposed. This law coupled to a chosen failure criteria delivers a first estimation of foam lifetime in operational conditions.

KEYWORDS : syntactic foams, homogenization, hygro-mechanical constitutive law, wet ageing, damage, lifetime.

INTRODUCTION

Syntactic foam is a composite material made of tiny hollow glass micro spheres embedded in a polymeric matrix. For structural Offshore applications, this material is a natural choice since it combines high buoyancy to strength at high pressures. Moreover, their thermal efficiency and water resistance make them a major actor for insulating sub-sea equipment. The required lifetime, which is still accompanied by uncertainties, requires a prediction of long-term behavior of this material under particularly operating conditions. In deep sea, the principal parameters conditioning the syntactic foam lifetime appear as the mechanical requirements that the structures have to undergo in such aggressive environment. Difficulties come primarily from the heterogeneous character of the composite material, location for many physico-chemical interactions occurring on very wide time scales. In particular, it is largely established that glass micro spheres are subject to humid corrosion under such operational conditions. This phenomenon, occurring in microstructure, can lead to significant reduction of the structure lifetime [1, 2]. Possible explanation calls upon the activation of the process of aqueous corrosion of glass micro spheres. Here we deliberately let apart chemical actions on the polymeric matrix to focus our work on the glass material.

The objective of this work is to seek a better understanding of the influence of operational conditions on the long-term behavior of immersed syntactic foams to estimate their lifetime. For that purpose, a study of the phenomenon of transport of moisture in composite materials was carried out and coupled with a modeling of the aqueous corrosion of glass micro spheres.

The microstructure evolution controlled by the kinetics of glass corrosion as given in literature [1] is determined. The knowledge of the microstructure allows to evaluate the equivalent macroscopic material using homogenization techniques, especially generalized self-consistent scheme. A four-phase modeling is developed taking into account the presence of corroded glass controlled by the water concentration in material.

The evolution of an equivalent constitutive law of immersed syntactic foams is then obtained everywhere in the studied structure at anytime. The field distribution of the stress and the stress concentration area in the microstructure have been studied [3]. The strength failure has also been determined using a given failure criterion for glass micro-spheres. The failure of the microstructure is directly transposed at the macroscopic level on the assumption of a size mono dispersion of the spheres. The state of failure on material is translated into a practical damage variable that is more tractable at the macroscopic level. Locally, the damaged state of the Representative Volume Elementary (RVE) is determined leading to an estimation of the local lifetime of the material according to the applied pressure. Thanks to ABAQUS[4], Finite Element Method code, the modeling is applied on a practical structure design to estimate its onset of failure under operating conditions.

GOVERNING EQUATIONS

To obtain the equivalent behavior of syntactic foams, the homogenization method used in this work is the generalized self-coherent method [5]. Four phases are distinguished in the RVE which consists of a single composite sphere surrounded by an infinite homogeneous medium of unknown elastic constants. The composite sphere is defined by an inner hollow spherical shell, made by the filler material, surrounded by a shell of matrix material. In the sequel, any considered material is assumed to be linear elastic.

Figure 1 : The RVE on the four phase scheme.

The equivalent behavior is then obtained by solving the hygro mechanical problem posed on the RVE defined on Figure 1. This RVE is subjected to a given macroscopic deformation \mathbf{E} and a macroscopic increment of moisture. In denoting the microscopic fields of displacements, relative weight and stresses by $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{y})$, Δm and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{y})$, the cellular problem to be solved for the described RVE can be written in the following form :

$$\operatorname{div} \boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{y}) = \mathbf{0}, \quad \text{in } V^e = V^i \cup V^m \cup V^*,$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{y}) = A(\mathbf{y}) : (e(\mathbf{y}) - \alpha(\mathbf{y}) \Delta m \mathbf{I}), \quad \text{in } V^e,$$

$$e(\mathbf{y}) = \frac{1}{2} (\nabla \mathbf{u} + {}^t \nabla \mathbf{u})(\mathbf{y}), \quad \text{in } V^e,$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{y}) \cdot \mathbf{n} = \mathbf{0}, \quad \text{on the edge of } \tilde{V},$$

$$u(\mathbf{y}) = E \cdot y, \quad \text{on the edge of } V,$$

where V^e is the part of volume V occupied by the three elastic phases, V^i for inclusion, V^m for matrix, V^* for equivalent medium and \tilde{V} for the volume occupied by the pore, where \mathbf{n} represents the unitary normal outside of \tilde{V} .

Once the problem is solved, the equivalent constitutive law is then obtained by :

$$\Sigma = \sigma^* = A^* : (E - \alpha^* \Delta m \mathbf{I}).$$

The resolution of this cellular problem is explicit and allows the determination of the microscopic stress fields in any phase. However, this method (based on the four phase scheme), like the majority of the analytical approaches, is limited to composites with low rates of filling, [6]. A proposed iterative process overcomes this difficulty and gives an estimation of the macroscopic constitutive law of syntactic foam even with high volume fraction of inclusions. Confrontations of the four phase modeling results with and without iterative process and those obtained from the method of periodic homogenization [3] are then proposed.

AN ITERATIVE METHOD OF HOMOGENIZATION OF COMPOSITE WITH HOLLOW SPHERICAL INCLUSIONS

In deep sea applications, used syntactic foams are with high rates of inclusions, nearly 60 %. This facts urges us into using the introduced iterative process in order to better take into account the interaction between inclusions, [7] and to widen the validity of the analytical approaches. It takes as a starting point the idea of composite material manufacturing in which inclusions are introduced gradually into the matrix. Theoretically, this process is inspired on its principle from the homogenization method known as "differential schema", [8], [9]. Thus, a given composite of final rate of inclusions τ_i , is reached by the successive development of n intermediate composites obtained by adding a volume

fraction of inclusions $\Delta \tau^j$, such as $\sum_{j=1}^n \Delta \tau^j = \tau_i$, to the composite resulting from the preceding step.

The hygro elastic constitutive law of the intermediate composite at a given step k is determined by the four phase method where the modulus affected to the matrix is the one obtained by homogenization in the earlier step ($k-1$), where the volume fraction is given by :

$$\tau_i^{(k)} = \frac{\Delta \tau^k}{\tau_m + \sum_{j=1}^k \Delta \tau^j} \quad \text{Eqn. 1}$$

In practice, at the step k , the equivalent elastic constitutive law, for example $A^{*(k)}$, is obtained after solving the cellular problem set for the representative volume. This method is repetitive and ends when the required volume fraction of inclusions is achieved.

APPLICATION TO THE IMMERSSED SYNTACTIC FOAMS

The syntactic foams are made of epoxy resin embedding hollow glass micro-spheres. Table 1 reports principal hygro mechanical data used in computations.

Component	Young modulus(Gpa.)	Poisson coefficient	Diffusion coefficient (mm ² .week ⁻¹)	Expansion coefficient
Matrix	$E_m : 3.5$	$\nu_m : 0.4$	$D_m : 1.512$	$\alpha_m : 3.2 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Glass	$E_g : 72$	$\nu_g : 0.22$	0	0

Table 1 : Mechanical parameters for components

The equivalent hygro elastic behavior of a syntactic foams was calculated for various inclusion concentrations. Here all micro-spheres are considered of same ratio thickness over the diameter, e/d . A comparison of the results obtained by the method of the four phase modeling with and without iterative process to those obtained by the method of homogenization of the periodic media, [10], was carried out. Figure 2 illustrates the difference between these two methods, expressed as relative error, which reaches 15 % , for the shear modulus in direct computation and nearly 5.5 % with iterative process for a given volume fraction of micro spheres equal to 60 %. Moreover, on Figure 3, the same comparison was carried out for the hygroscopic coefficient of expansion of syntactic foams. The use of the four phase modeling with the iterative method reduces remarkably the relative error on effective hygro elastic modulus of syntactic foams compared to the periodic approach. One more advantage of this iterative process is its easy implementation compared to the periodic method.

Figure 2 : Relative error between periodic homogenization and four phase scheme for shear modulus with and without iterative computation versus volume fraction of micro spheres.

Figure 3 : Relative error between periodic homogenization and four phase scheme for hygroscopic coefficient of expansion with and without iterative computation versus volume fraction of micro spheres.

The elastic local stresses, resulting from a macroscopic imposed load of 30 MPa , corresponding to the pressure of service at 3000 m of sea depth, are obtained by the four phase method with and without iterations. They are confronted on Figure 4 in the case of direct and iterative calculations and through the various phases of the RVE (inclusion, matrix and composite). Resulting from unitary macroscopic imposed variation of humidity, the radial components of the local stresses for both methods are described on Figure 5.

It can be noticed that the contribution of the iterative process is maximum especially at the interface inclusion-matrix compared to the direct process. Moreover, one can stress out that at the interface between the inclusion and the matrix ($r/b = 1$), both radial stresses reach their maximum values. It means that inclusions undergo maximum radial loads onto their exterior surfaces. It is worth also checking that radial stresses, induced by a hydrostatic pressure and by a unitary macroscopic change of humidity, have the same order of magnitude. So in the sequel, we shall not be allowed to neglect one phenomenon over the other.

Figure 4 : Radial component of local stresses obtained by direct and iterative computations for a macroscopic compression loading versus ratio r/b .

Figure 5 : Radial component of local stresses obtained by direct and iterative computations for a unitary macroscopic hygrosopic load versus ratio r/b .

MODELLING OF THE AGEING PHENOMENON OF MICRO-SPHERES

The physico-chemical ageing phenomenon of glass micro balloons in marine environment, observed in experiments [11], is modeled here by the distinction between a healthy layer of glass and a corroded one made of silica gel. The created interface is propagated inside the material with an interfacial speed, v , controlled by the chemical reaction.

Over the whole surface of each micro-spheres, the interfacial speed, v , is assumed constant and is directly proportional to the surface of the reaction interface. As a chemical damage parameter, the advance chemical rate, τ_s , is introduced, it is defined by the ratio of the used glass mass compared to the initial glass mass. Under this assumption, the chemical kinetics of corrosion results in the relation given in equation below [12] :

$$\tau_s(t) = \frac{m_s(0) - m_s(t)}{m_s(0)} = \text{Inf} \left[1, 1 - \left(1 - t \cdot \frac{\Delta_c}{3}\right)^3 \right] \quad \text{Eqn. 2}$$

where $m_s(t)$ indicates the healthy mass of glass at the moment t , $m_s(0)$ the mass of initial operational glass and $\Delta_c = \frac{6v}{d}$ is a constant characterizing the kinetics of leaching of glass. This constant is valued $9.340 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ week}^{-1}$ which corresponds to a grade of glass used in the field of radioactive waste storage, [13] at a constant temperature (90° C). The exterior diameter of micro spheres is fixed at $120 \mu\text{m}$. Only the chemical damage parameter is responsible for the time control of the ageing and is a direct time dependent function.

FORECAST OF THE DAMAGE

At a material point, the phenomenon of glass corrosion is initiated at the moment when the moisture interface reaches this point. At any later moment, the thickness of the corroded layer glass of the micro spheres will change and will be determined thanks to the kinetics of the chemical reaction. At this step the homogenized behavior of composite integrating this new phase is then carried out according to the principle previously exposed.

Figure 6 : Evolution of the microscopic pressure applied on the micro sphere and the pressure of Timoshenko versus the damage parameter D .

The local stresses are also updated, revealing the zone of possible weakness of the micro spheres. This weakness is estimated thanks to the critical pressure of buckling of a spherical reservoir subjected to hydrostatic pressures, [1]. If P is the radial stress applied on the micro sphere, e_c the thickness of the corroded layer and e the initial glass thickness, the resistance is given by :

$$D = \frac{e_c}{e} = 1 - \frac{f(P)}{1 - f(P)} \left(\frac{d}{e} - 2 \right), \text{ where } f(P) = \sqrt{\frac{P \sqrt{3(1 - \nu_g^2)}}{8E_g}} \quad \text{Eqn. 3}$$

On Figure 6, are presented the evolution of this critical pressure of buckling and that of the pressure applied on the micro balloon, σ_{rr} , according to the proportion of corroded glass. For a micro sphere of size ratio $e/d = 0.02$ and an operating pressure of 30 MPa , it appears that, for a 70 % corroded rate of glass, the micro spheres collapse. The conversion of damage into lifetime is obtained by exploiting the formulation delivered in the chemical section (Eqn.2) and the following linkage formula :

$$\tau_s = \frac{1 - \left(1 - 2 \frac{e}{d} D \right)^3}{1 - \left(1 - 2 \frac{e}{d} \right)^3} \quad \text{Eqn. 4}$$

In our example, the expected lifetime of the micro structure (micro spheres) is about 16 years after the water has appeared into the material. The temperature is also maintained constant at 90°C .

STRUCTURAL APPLICATION

In this section, the previous development is applied to a structure analysis. The obtained constitutive law is implemented numerically into a commercial Finite Element Method code (ABAQUS [4]). The selected homogeneous material is determined after 100 iterations of the homogenization process described in a previous section. The method is here applied in the field of mechanics but also in the hygroscopic field to deliver the diffusion coefficient and the hygroscopic expansion coefficient according the chemical rate. It means that for every elements of the meshing the homogenized properties of foam are used and updated with the evolution of the chemical rate.

The properties of intrinsic materials are those reported on table 1. The simple structure studied is a tube made of syntactic foams immersed with an inside radius of 12 inches and a 200 mm thickness (see figure 7). The inside wall of the tube is applied on rigid tube without friction the material in this location is assumed dry . On the outside wall, the service pressure 30 MPa (300 bar) is applied on the overall surface and the outside surface is dry but a 100 mm height section in the middle which is in contact with water (Yellow zone on Figure 7).

The structure analysis depicts the incidental case where the watertight coating has a defect on the outside wall. The computational analysis is run over 20 years (1040 weeks). In the sequel, results are reported to describe the evolution of the syntactic foam close to the defect. The chemical rate is reported on figure 8 at various time. It is necessary to point out that the analysis at this moment describes the material till the first appearance of a micro sphere collapse.

Figure 7 : Mechanical properties according chemical damage and structure geometry.

In the middle of the defect along the pipe thickness, the hygroscopic and the total strain are reported as the chemical rate at various time on figure 8. The results confirm the necessity to handle the expansion strain due to the water absorption of the matrix. By exploiting the equation (Eqn.3) and assuming the micro spheres close to the outside of the pipe are under a 30 MPa pressure, it makes sense to consider 15 years as a rough estimation of the surface lifetime of the pipe. To refine this value, it is necessary in a next step to introduce the localization of stress from the macroscopic (FEM element) to the microscopic (micro spheres surface) level within the FEM development. It means that the calculations of micro stresses thanks to the iterative homogenization scheme must be included.

Figure 8 : Strain and chemical rate inside the defect zone.

Figure 9 : *Strain inside the defect zone.*

CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLINES

The iterative process applied to the four phase modeling allows to reduce noticeably errors on hygro elastic constitutive law of syntactic foams. Moreover the method brings a correction of micro structural stresses especially at the interface inclusion–matrix. The failure criterion based upon these more accurate stresses delivers a better forecast for the onset of material ruin. Here the modeling of the damage was focussed on a description of the wet ageing of glass. The only parameter of damage exploited in this application is related to the progressive growth of a corroded layer around glass micro spheres according to a chemical reaction involving water absorption. With a population of identical micro spheres, a rough estimate of the material lifetime is obtained under the sole influence of glass chemistry. Other influences can interact in this ageing process and require later works. Here we may quote statistical fracture of glass, chemical action of water on the epoxy matrix. Enrichment of the geometrical description of micro structure is another research path to take into account the size distribution of the micro spheres as it occurs in syntactic foams. Actually this point is under process by adapting the iterative method of homogenization used in the present paper. Finally, to feed and to validate the present modeling, experimental characterizations of the various phenomena are needed.

REFERENCES

- [1] R.J. Charles, Static Fatigue of Glass. I, Journal of Applied Physics, Vol. 29, N°11, 1549-1553, 1958.
- [2] B. Dewimille and A. R. Bunsell., Accelerated ageing of a glass fiber-reinforced epoxy resin in water, Composites, January, 1983.
- [3] A. Benhamida, H. Dumontet, F. Léné, Modelling of the failure surface of syntactic foams by a micro-macro approach, Ninth International Conference on Composites, San Diego, July 1-6, 2002.
- [4] ABAQUS, HKS Inc., Providence, RI, 2001.
- [5] R. M. Christensen, Mechanics of Composite Materials, A. Wiley-Interscience Publication, 1979
- [6] M. Bornert, T. Bretheau, and P. Gilormini, Homogénéisation en mécanique des matériaux, ed. Hermès Science, 2001.
- [7] A. Ben Hamida, H. Dumontet, and A. Lekhder, Un modèle de comportement hygroscopique des mousses syntactiques, Revue des composites et des matériaux avancés., Vol. 8, N° 1, 73-90, 1998.
- [8] J. Aboudi, Mechanics of Composite Materials, ed. Elsevier, 1991.
- [9] A. N. Norris, A differential schema for the effective moduli of composites, Mechanics of Materials, Vol 4, 1-16, 1985.
- [10] A. Ben Hamida, Comportement micro mécanique des mousses syntactiques, Thèse de l'Université Pierre et Marie Curie, 1989.
- [11] A. Avena, and A. R. Bunsell, Comportement à long terme de matériaux composites en immersion sous pression hydrostatique. Comptes rendus des Cinquièmes Journées Nationales des Composites., Pluralis Editor, pp. 409-426, 1986.
- [12] B. Delmon, Introduction à la cinétique hétérogène, Editions Technip, Paris, 1969.
- [13] I. Tovenà, Influence de la composition des verres nucléaires sur leur altérabilité, Thèse d'Université de Montpellier II, 1995.
- [14] S.P. Timoshenko, Théorie de la stabilité élastique, Librairie Polytechnique, CH. Beranger, Paris-Liège, 1947.